

Einstein Meets Economics

Amazon Book Review Series of “*Better Economics for the Earth: A Lesson from Quantum and Information Theories*”

Stacy Gragnani

December 29, 2024

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A book that dares to bridge the gap between quantum physics and economic theory in a truly illuminating way. The authors weave together complex scientific principles with economic thought, presenting a fresh perspective on how we might better steward our planet's resources. Interesting stuff.

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Screenshot. Review of “*Better Economics for the Earth*” by Gragnani [1]. Reviewed in the United States on December 29, 2024.

(*) Note: This paper reprints Gragnani’s review [1] appearing on the Amazon page of the title [2].

References

[1] Gragnani, S. (2024, Dec. 29). Einstein Meets Economics. <https://www.amazon.com/gp/customer-reviews/R2GC7JOA3F8C5W/>

[2] Vuong, Q. H. & Nguyen, M. H. (2024). *Better Economics for the Earth: A Lesson from Quantum and Information Theories*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/B0D98L5K44>